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Abstract

Aim

To evaluate the performance of a state-of-the-art cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) artefact suppression method by assessing to what extent the filtered electrocardiogram (ECG) can be correctly diagnosed by emergency medicine doctors.

Methods

A total of 819 ECG segments were used. Each segment contained two consecutive 10 s intervals, an artefact free interval and an interval corrupted by CPR artefacts. Each ECG segment was digitally processed to remove CPR artefacts using an adaptive filter. Each ECG segment was split into artefact-free and filtered intervals, randomly reordered for dissociation, and independently offered to four reviewers for rhythm annotation. The rhythm annotations of the artefact-free intervals were considered as the gold standard against which the rhythm annotations of the filtered intervals were evaluated. For the filtered intervals, the rater agreement (κ , Kappa score) with the gold standard, the sensitivity and the specificity were computed individually for each reviewer, and jointly through the majority decision of the pool of reviewers (DPR). These results were also compared to those obtained using a commercial shock advisory algorithm (SAA).

Results

The agreement between each reviewer and the gold standard was moderate ranging between $\kappa = 0.41$ – 0.64 . The sensitivities and specificities ranged between 64.3–95.0%, and 70.0–95.9%, respectively. The agreement for the DPR was substantial with $\kappa = 0.64$ (0.62–0.66), a sensitivity of 90.6%, and a specificity of 85.6%. For the SAA, the agreement was fair with $\kappa = 0.33$ (0.31–0.35), a sensitivity of 90.3%, and a specificity of 66.4%.

Conclusion

Clinicians outperformed the SAA, but specificities remained below the specifications recommended by the American Heart Association. Visual assessment of the filtered ECG by clinicians is not reliable enough, and varies greatly among clinicians. Results considerably improve by considering the consensus decision of a pool of clinicians.

Keywords: Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), Rhythm analysis during CPR, CPR artefact suppression, Adaptive filter

Evaluation of chest compression artefact removal based on rhythm assessments made by clinicians

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Conclusion: Clinicians outperformed the SAA, but specificities remained below the specifications recommended by the American Heart Association. Visual assessment of the filtered ECG by clinicians is not reliable enough, and varies greatly among clinicians. Results considerably improve by considering the consensus decision of a pool of clinicians.

Keywords

Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), rhythm analysis during CPR, CPR artefact suppression, adaptive filter

1. INTRODUCTION

The analysis of the heart rhythm during cardiac arrest is determinant because the actions to be taken depend on the ongoing rhythm. Current advanced life support (ALS) guidelines recommend (1) attempting defibrillation and immediately after, resuming cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) in patients presenting shockable rhythms (ventricular fibrillation, VF; or pulseless ventricular tachycardia, VT), and simply resuming CPR in patients with non-shockable rhythms (asystole, AS; and pulseless-electrical activity, PEA).^{1,2} CPR includes, in addition to other interventions, high-quality chest compressions which introduce artefacts in the electrocardiogram (ECG) that make rhythm analysis unreliable.^{3,4} Therefore, chest compressions must be interrupted to allow for a reliable rhythm analysis. These interruptions increase hands-off interval which is detrimental for the patient as it negatively affects the probability of return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC),^{5,6} and survival.⁷⁻¹¹

The suppression of the CPR artefact would make rhythm analysis during CPR possible and consequently, would minimize interruptions in chest compressions and enhance the chance of survival. In the last two decades, different methods have been proposed to achieve this goal. Most of them are based on adaptive filtering techniques that estimate the time-varying artefact using additional reference signal(s), and then subtract it from the corrupt ECG to obtain a filtered ECG free of CPR artefacts.^{4,12-16} To evaluate the performance of these methods, the filtered ECG is analyzed by a shock advisory algorithm (SAA) to obtain the sensitivity (SE, capacity to correctly detect shockable rhythms) and specificity (SP, capacity to correctly detect non-shockable rhythms) of the method. Despite recent advances,^{17,18} current methods do not meet the minimum SE/SP requirements established by the American Heart Association (AHA).¹⁹ Although the great majority of methods showed sensitivities above the 90% minimum value recommended by the AHA, they showed specificities around 85% which is well below the 95% recommended minimum value. Therefore, the combination of CPR artefact suppression method with the SAA of a defibrillator, i.e. a fully-automatic method for a shock/no-shock decision, is not currently feasible.^{20,21}

In this paper we assess a semi-automatic alternative where a CPR artefact suppression method would be combined with the rhythm diagnosis by experienced clinicians. In ALS, this might be incorporated into monitor/defibrillators as an additional functionality which the healthcare personnel could activate by pushing a button. The filtered ECG would then be displayed together

31 with the corrupt ECG and the estimated CPR artefact. The clinician might continuously assess
32 the rhythm during CPR and only decide to stop CPR in order to (1) advance defibrillation because
33 a shockable rhythm is detected or (2) confirm in an artefact-free interval the suspected shockable
34 rhythm. Therefore, the aim of this study is to evaluate the accuracy of emergency medicine doctors
35 diagnosing the filtered ECG obtained via a state-of-the-art CPR artefact suppression method.

36 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

37 2.1. Data materials

38 The data used in this study is a subset of an out-of-hospital cardiac arrest database composed
39 of 238 episodes, one per patient, that were collected by the Tualatin Valley Fire & Rescue (Tigard,
40 Oregon, USA) using the Philips HeartStart MRx monitor/defibrillator between January 2013 and
41 December 2014. Each episode contained the ECG signal acquired through the defibrillation pads
42 and the compression depth (CD) signal extracted from the CPR assist pad. ECG segments were
43 extracted from the episodes when the following two consecutive 10s intervals were found: an
44 artefact-free interval followed by an interval with CPR artefact, or viceversa. All the available
45 segments, a total of 819, containing ECG and CD signals were used in the study. These numbers
46 are comparable or larger than the number of segments used to assess rhythm analysis during CPR
47 using automatic algorithms.^{4,14–17,22} Fig. 1 shows an example of an ECG segment presenting VF.
48 The top panel shows the complete ECG, where the first and last 10s correspond to the corrupt
49 and artefact-free intervals respectively.

50 2.2. CPR artefact suppression

51 ECG segments were digitally processed to remove the CPR artefact using an adaptive filtering
52 scheme based on the least mean square (LMS) algorithm.^{15,23,24} This method first estimates the
53 CPR artefact, $cpr(n)$, and then subtracts it from the corrupt ECG to obtain the filtered ECG. In
54 essence, the CPR artefact is considered as a quasi-periodic interference that can be modelled by
55 its Fourier series representation:

$$cpr(n) = \sum_{k=1}^N a_k(n) \cos(2\pi k f(n)n) + b_k(n) \sin(2\pi k f(n)n) \quad (1)$$

56 where N represents the number of harmonics of the model, $a_k(n)$ and $b_k(n)$ correspond to the
57 in-phase and quadrature Fourier coefficients, and $f(n)$, is the instantaneous frequency of the CPR
58 artefact (chest compressions). Note that $f(n)$, $a_k(n)$, and $b_k(n)$ are time-varying, and $f(n)$ varies
59 from compression cycle to cycle, but remains constant within each cycle. The frequency $f(n)$ is
60 computed as the inverse of the time interval between chest compressions which are detected using
61 a simple negative peak detector in the CD signal. On the other hand, $a_k(n)$ and $b_k(n)$ vary from

62 sample to sample, and are computed using the LMS algorithm.^{23,24} The CPR suppression method
63 has two design parameters: N , and the step size of the LMS algorithm, μ_0 . These values were set
64 to $N=5$ and $\mu_0=0.0178$ following the original authors.¹⁵

65 *2.3. Rhythm annotation*

66 Rhythm annotations were made independently by four emergency medicine doctors (authors
67 MD, CC, YL, AI) from different international sites. Doctors are members of resuscitation teams
68 which routinely treat cardiac arrest patients in- and/or out-of hospital. Reviewers classified the
69 rhythm as VF or VT in the shockable category, and as AS or organized rhythm (OR) in the
70 non-shockable category. The rhythm was classified as undecided (UN) if the segment presented:
71 (1) an intermediate rhythm for which there is no clear shock/no-shock recommendation (fine VF
72 and slow VT),¹⁹ (2) a rhythm transition, or (3) large movement artefacts.

73 Each ECG segment was split into artefact-free and filtered intervals, randomly reordered to
74 dissociate the intervals, and independently offered to each of the reviewers.

75 *2.3.1. Gold standard and dataset of the study*

76 The consensus shock/no-shock diagnosis of at least three reviewers during the artefact-free
77 interval was considered as the correct diagnosis for the whole ECG segment (artefact-free +
78 corrupt). That is, the gold standard against which to compare the shock/no-shock diagnosis
79 of the filtered interval. Since both data subsets (artefact-free and corrupt) were dissociated and
80 randomly reordered, the annotation phases for the gold standard and the rhythm assessment during
81 CPR were considered independent. Segments with split decisions in the artefact-free interval were
82 discarded from the dataset of the study. Panel a of Fig. 2 shows an example of an artefact-free
83 interval (OR) of an ECG segment exactly as it was offered for annotation to the reviewers. Panel
84 b of Fig. 1 depicts an artefact-free interval of an ECG segment included in the dataset of the study
85 as it was annotated unanimously as VF by all the reviewers.

86 *2.3.2. Filtered intervals*

87 The filtered intervals of the dataset of the study were dissociated from the artefact-free intervals
88 and their order randomized before being offered for annotation to the reviewers. For each filtered
89 interval, reviewers were provided with the filtered ECG, the corrupt ECG, and the estimated CPR
90 artefact to make the decision, in the form shown in panel b of Fig. 2. In addition, a consensus

91 decision, designated as the diagnosis of the pool of reviewers (DPR), was defined when at least three
92 reviewers agreed on the shock/no-shock diagnosis of the filtered interval. Filtered intervals without
93 sufficient agreement in the DPR were labelled as UN. The DPR represents the consensus diagnosis
94 of the filtered intervals that would provide the maximum performance (SE/SP) achievable. It is
95 very unlikely that individual performances outperform that obtained by the DPR. Panel a of Fig.
96 1 represents, from top to bottom, the corrupt ECG, filtered ECG and estimated CPR artefact of a
97 filtered interval annotated unanimously as VF by all the reviewers, and therefore, included in the
98 DPR as shockable.

99 *2.4. Diagnostic accuracy and statistical analysis*

100 The reviewers' accuracy for shock/no-shock diagnosis was evaluated in terms of SE and SP, and
101 was compared to that obtained by the SAA currently running on the Reanibex R-series defibrillators
102 (Bexen Cardio, Ermua, Spain). The SAA is AHA compliant and diagnoses the rhythm in less than
103 9.6 s by analyzing 2 or 3 consecutive 3.2 s intervals of the ECG.²⁵ Finally, for the shock/no-shock
104 annotation the inter-rater agreement, and the agreement between raters and the gold standard
105 were measured using the Fleiss' Kappa coefficient (κ) and its 95% confidence interval.

106 3. RESULTS

107 From the 819 segments annotated, only 755 (611 non-shockable and 144 shockable) were
108 included in the dataset of the study, and 64 were discarded because of the lack for a shock/no-shock
109 decision in the artefact free interval. Fig. 3 shows five examples of ECG segments not included
110 in the dataset of the study. From top to bottom, (1) an interval with two shockable and two
111 non-shockable diagnoses, (2) a border case where half of the reviewers could not make a decision and
112 the other half disagreed, (3) a rhythm transition from VF to AS, (4) a VT which was misdiagnosed
113 as OR by half of the reviewers, and (5) a noisy interval that half of the reviewers annotated as UN.

114 Table 1 summarizes the results obtained for the artefact-free intervals. The agreement achieved
115 between reviewers for the 755 segments that composed the dataset of the study was almost
116 perfect with $\kappa=0.89$ (0.89-0.90). The agreement between each reviewer (A, B, C and D) and
117 the gold standard ranged between $\kappa=0.91$ -0.98. The SE and SP of the reviewers ranged between
118 90.2%-100%, and 96.4%-99.7%, respectively. The mean proportion of intervals diagnosed as UN by
119 the reviewers was very low (1.3%). The performance of the SAA was AHA compliant resulting in
120 a SE and SP of 94.4% and 95.4% respectively. The agreement of the SAA with the gold standard
121 was also almost perfect with a Kappa score of $\kappa=0.85$ (0.83-0.87).

122 Table 2 summarizes the results obtained for the filtered intervals. The agreement between
123 each reviewer (A, B, C and D) and the gold standard was moderate, the mean kappa score of
124 the four reviewers was $\kappa=0.53$ (range 0.41-0.64). The SE and SP of the reviewers ranged between
125 64.3%-95.0%, and 70.0%-95.9%, respectively. The mean proportion of intervals diagnosed as UN
126 by the reviewers was 7.8%. The agreement of the consensus decision (DPR) and the gold standard
127 was substantial with a $\kappa=0.64$ (0.62-0.66), a SE of 90.6%, an SP of 85.6%, and a proportion of
128 intervals diagnosed as UN of 16.2%. Finally, the performance of the SAA was AHA compliant
129 only for the SE (90.3%), while SP decreased to 66.4%. The agreement of the SAA with the gold
130 standard was fair with a Kappa score of $\kappa=0.33$ (0.31-0.35). In order to make a fair comparison
131 between the DPR and the SAA, the latter was run on the 633 segments diagnosed by the DPR
132 resulting in a SE/SP of 93.7%/73.7%.

133 4. DISCUSSION

134 In this paper, the feasibility of rhythm analysis during ongoing CPR was evaluated through the
135 visual assessment of the ECG made by experienced emergency medicine doctors. A state-of-the-art
136 method was used to eliminate the artefact due to chest compressions and the resulting filtered ECG,
137 together with the estimated CPR artefact and the corrupt ECG, was diagnosed by four emergency
138 medicine doctors. The diagnoses were compared with the consensus diagnosis of the adjacent
139 artefact-free ECG segments, and the SE, SP, and the rater agreements computed.

140 *4.1. The dataset of the study and the gold standard*

141 The dataset of the study contained 755 ECG segments in which a consensus shock/no-shock
142 diagnosis was reached in the artefact-free interval. The remaining 64 segments provided no
143 consensus and were excluded in an effort to obtain a robust gold standard. The artefact-free
144 intervals of those excluded intervals were not further reviewed to reach a consensus shock/no-shock
145 diagnosis because a reliable rhythm annotation cannot be obtained by forcing an agreement
146 in intervals presenting rhythm transitions, borderline rhythms and/or artefacted ECGs. The
147 robustness and reliability of the resulting gold standard were evident as both the agreement
148 achieved between the four reviewers ($\kappa=0.89$), and the agreement of the SAA with the gold standard
149 ($\kappa=0.85$) were almost perfect.

150 *4.2. Rhythm analysis accuracy*

151 Overall, the assessment of the filtered intervals by the reviewers reported better results than
152 those obtained by the SAA. The agreement with the gold standard was moderate (mean $\kappa=0.53$)
153 for each reviewer individually, and substantial ($\kappa=0.64$) for the DPR, while the agreement between
154 the SAA and gold standard was just fair ($\kappa=0.33$). The SE and SP showed by reviewers individually
155 and by the DPR were also above those obtained by the SAA. However, the results reported for
156 the reviewers and for the DPR did not take into account the proportion of intervals diagnosed as
157 UN, a mean of 7.8% and 16.2% respectively. The UN diagnoses reflect a situation in which the
158 clinician decides that a diagnosis is not possible based on the traces displayed. Conversely, in the
159 results reported for the SAA, all the intervals were analyzed since defibrillators are programmed
160 to always give a shock/no-shock diagnosis and cannot postpone the decision. When the SAA was
161 run on the 633 segments diagnosed by the DPR, the performance of the SAA improved (SE/SP of

162 93.7%/73.7%) but remained well below that obtained by the DPR. Nevertheless, the SAA used in
163 this study runs on a commercial defibrillator and was therefore designed to diagnose artefact-free
164 intervals. It is possible that a SAA optimized to diagnose filtered ECGs, such as that proposed by
165 Ayala et al.,¹⁸ may show better performance.

166 The mean values of the SE and SP obtained by the clinicians were good, but the individual
167 performance varied significantly among them. The balanced accuracy, the mean of the SE and SP,
168 was similar for all clinicians (between 80.4%-83.8%), but the differences in SE and SP were large
169 among clinicians. Reviewers A (SE/SP 88.1%/79.3%) and C (86.3%/81.3%) showed balanced SE
170 and SP, whereas Reviewer B (95.0%/70.0%) and D (64.3%/95.9%) showed marked tendency to
171 either shock or not-shock, respectively. These differences in the individual performance might be
172 caused by variations in training and treatment strategies among sites.

173 This is the first time that rhythm analysis during CPR is assessed based on the decisions made
174 by clinicians, so there is no other similar study against which to compare our results. However, to
175 get the sense of a comparison, our results in terms of SE/SP are similar to those reported for other
176 authors that used SAAs to carry out the evaluation: Eilevstjønn et al.⁴ (96.7%/79.9%), Ruiz de
177 Gauna et al.¹⁴ (90.1%/80.4%), Aramendi et al.²² (95.4%/86.3%), Li et al.²⁶ (93.3%/88.6%), Tan
178 et al.²⁷ (92.1%/90.5%), or Krasteva et al.²⁸ (90.1%/86.1%). In all these studies specificities were
179 well below the 95% goal recommended by the AHA. However, this comparison must be considered
180 carefully as each work (1) was carried out on a different dataset with different rhythm prevalences,
181 and (2) used its own SAA which may diagnose the filtered ECG in a different way. Fig. 4 shows
182 the main reasons for the misdiagnoses. In panel a, the main reason of the low specificity of this
183 and previous studies is illustrated, an AS diagnosed as shockable due to the residue left by the
184 filtering process. In panel b, a source of erroneous non-shockable decisions is shown, spiky filtering
185 residuals interpreted as QRS complexes for a VF.

186 *4.3. Current state and potential application*

187 Currently, to the best of our knowledge, there are two commercial technologies that offer rhythm
188 assessment during ongoing CPR. The first one corresponds to the CPR artefact suppression method
189 proposed by Tan et al.²⁷ (known as 'See-Thru CPR') which has been incorporated into commercial
190 defibrillators, namely Zoll Medical Corporation (Chelmsford, Massachusetts, USA) defibrillators.
191 It displays on defibrillator's screen both the filtered ECG and the estimated CPR artifact during

192 ongoing chest compressions and only if the operating mode is set to manual. Thus, only professional
193 rescuers able to operate in manual mode can see the filtered ECG during chest compressions.
194 According to the manufacturer, the filtered ECG is not suitable for making treatment decisions
195 because the 'See-Thru CPR' is not able to remove all the CPR artefact. Therefore, CPR must be
196 always stopped to reassess the rhythm and make a decision.

197 The second and most recent one is the 'cprINSIGHT' analysis technology incorporated in the
198 automated external defibrillator LIFEPAK CR2 by Physio-Control (Redmond, WA, USA). The
199 technology is proprietary and few details have been disclosed, only that it processes both ECG
200 and thoracic impedance during ongoing compressions, and one of the following three decisions is
201 made: shock, no shock, or to pause chest compressions because further analysis (in an artefact-free
202 interval) is required.²⁹

203 Given the SE/SP values observed for individual reviewers and for the DPR, our study confirms
204 that the filtered ECG should be used as a decision support tool during ALS. That is, the
205 combination of CPR artefact suppression and visual assessment of filtered ECG by doctors is quite
206 good, but not enough to meet AHA requirements. Nevertheless, if applied correctly our method
207 can be helpful to minimize hands-off intervals and advance defibrillation in ALS. For instance,
208 during 2 min chest compressions series ALS providers could monitor the rhythm at any time and
209 make one of the following decisions: (1) charge the defibrillator and immediately after, stop CPR
210 before the end of the series to confirm the suspected shockable rhythm in an artefact-free interval.
211 If so, deliver a shock and otherwise, discharge the defibrillator and resume chest compressions; (2)
212 prolong chest compressions because a clear OR is detected. Only stop chest compressions when a
213 rhythm transition occurs and a rhythm reassessment is needed, or when pulse must be checked;
214 (3) if none of the previous actions take place, complete the chest compression series and then make
215 a diagnosis in an artefact-free interval. Future studies must validate this application proposal
216 with simulations of real cardiac arrest episodes to quantify the reduction of hands-off intervals
217 (shortening pre-shock pauses or avoiding unnecessary rhythm analysis intervals) and advance of
218 defibrillation. In a second stage, shock outcome prediction³⁰⁻³² might also be incorporated to this
219 application proposal to only deliver defibrillations with high probability of success and thus, avoid
220 unnecessary unsuccessful defibrillations that can cause myocardial damage.

221 4.4. *Limitations of the study*

222 This study was conceived to measure the accuracy of rhythm analysis by experienced emergency
223 medicine doctors when assessing the rhythm in a relaxed scenario, i.e. in optimal conditions
224 without the time restriction, stress and pressure that are present in a real cardiac arrest scenario.
225 Accuracy in rhythm assessment obtained in more stressful scenarios (with time restriction or in a
226 real scenario) is expected to be lower. Future studies must evaluate how visual ECG assessment
227 by emergency medicine doctors is affected with limited time for a decision.

228 Another limiting factor is that the study was carried out using data acquired from a particular
229 site and exclusively by the Philips MRx monitor/defibrillator. Therefore, results obtained should
230 be confirmed using data from different sites and ECGs recorded from a wide variety of defibrillators.

231 5. **Conclusions**

232 In this study, the reliability of rhythm analysis during ongoing CPR has been evaluated through
233 the visual assessment of the ECG by experienced emergency medicine doctors. An adaptive filtering
234 scheme based on the LMS algorithm has been used to suppress the CPR artefact, and the accuracy
235 of four experienced clinicians to diagnose the filtered ECG has been evaluated and compared to
236 that of a commercial SAA. Reviewers outperformed the SAA, but specificities remained below the
237 specifications recommended by the AHA. The decision of a pool of reviewers increased the accuracy
238 considerably.

239 **Ethical Approval**

240 The CPR process files used in this study were collected as part of an effort to develop an
241 airway check algorithm using the capnography signal. Since these raw data files have no identifying
242 information, the Institutional Review Board at the Oregon Health & Science University determined
243 that the proposed activity is not human subject research because the proposed activity does not
244 meet the definition of human subject per 45 CFR 46.102(f).

245 **Conflict of interest**

246 Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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327 Figure Legends

- 328 Figure 1 Example of a segment presenting VF which was included in the dataset
329 of the study. On top the complete ECG where the first 10s correspond
330 to the corrupt interval and the following 10s to the artefact-free
331 interval. Panel a shows, from top to bottom, the corrupt ECG
332 (ECG_c), filtered ECG (ECG_f), and estimated CPR artefact (CPR),
333 while panel b represents the artefact-free ECG (ECG_{af}).
- 334 Figure 2 Dissociated segment as it was presented to the reviewers for
335 annotation. The top panel shows 6s of the artefact-free interval,
336 while the bottom panel shows 6s of the filtered ECG which included
337 the corrupt ECG, the filtered ECG and the CPR artefact. The
338 intervals were numbered differently and delivered in separate booklets
339 to guarantee the dissociation.
- 340 Figure 3 Examples of artefact-free intervals of segments not included in the
341 dataset of the study. Annotations made by the four reviewers are
342 shown in the left-top side of the ECG.
- 343 Figure 4 Examples of ECG segments misdiagnosed after removing the CPR
344 artefact. In both panels, from top to bottom, the raw ECG where the
345 first 10s correspond to the artefact-free interval and the last 10s to
346 the corrupt interval, and the filtered ECG after removing the CPR
347 artefact. Panel a shows an AS misdiagnosed as shockable due to large
348 disorganized filtering residuals, and panel b depicts a VF incorrectly
349 diagnosed as non-shockable due to post-filtering spikes which were
350 interpreted as QRS complexes by the reviewers.

351 Table Legends

352 Table 1 Summary of the results obtained for the artefact-free intervals. The SE,
353 SP, proportion of intervals diagnosed as UN and the agreement with the
354 gold standard are reported for each reviewer (A, B, C, and D), and for
355 the SAA. The numbers in parenthesis indicate the positive decisions for
356 each category out of the total number of decisions. Kappa scores with
357 95% confidence intervals are reported to measure the agreement.

358 Table 2 Summary of the results obtained for the filtered intervals. The SE,
359 SP, proportion of intervals diagnosed as UN and the agreement with
360 the gold standard are reported for each reviewer (A, B, C, and D), for
361 the DPR, and for the SAA. The numbers in parenthesis indicate the
362 positive decisions for each category out of the total number of decisions.
363 Kappa scores with 95% confidence intervals are reported to measure the
364 agreement.